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Machine Learning Driven Selective Region-of-Interest Compression

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ABSTRACT

In this paper we present methods for incorporating information from the output of machine learning models into region-of-interest (RoI) aware compression algorithms. A number of approaches have been evaluated. These include the naive approach where the input image is decomposed into two images, the target and the context, which are subsequently compressed with lossless and lossy compression algorithms respectively. This is compared to more sophisticated approaches to RoI encoding, for example RoI-supportive variants of Set Partitioning in Hierarchical Trees (SPIHT) and CCSDS-122.0-B-2. A quantitative comparison of compression ratio has been performed for a selection of EO imagery with a highlighted RoI. Methods for selection of compression parameters are also discussed, as are their effects on output image quality. Finally, how these components fit together into an overall payload processing chain is presented. Some thoughts are given toward the hardware implementations of such schemes, whether they can be accelerated partially or fully in hardware, or whether this level of throughput is a requirement for all applications.

INTRODUCTION

The acquisition and transmission of remote sensing imagery for Earth observation is expensive both in terms of computation and bandwidth. There is growing interest in on-board data processing for Earth observation satellites, driven by the needs of downstream applications of satellite data and the challenges borne by the volumes of data collected by the latest instrument technologies. This trend is being driven by advances in sensors and the planned deployment of larger constellations of satellites to give more frequent coverage of areas of interest. Alongside this growth in data acquisition, there is no projected near-term increase in downlink capabilities from individual satellites. System architectures where all collected payload data is downlinked still dominate the traditional satellite market. Satellites, especially small satellites, are traditionally downlink constrained regarding the amount of data that they can deliver to users. Therefore, operational choices must be made about which data to prioritise for downlink.

These operational decisions, both scientific and technical, are traditionally performed on ground by large operations teams. As manufacture and launch costs are driven down, the number of satellites is expected to grow exponentially but operations teams cannot grow to such large sizes without a subsequent growth in operational costs. This necessitates levels of autonomy being introduced to the system to keep operational costs at a reasonable level. By introducing more on-board processing of payload data, the decision-making task can be simplified for the operator by the on-board extraction of interesting data from the stream. On-board processing activities which can extract information from data and prioritise useful information can not only deliver data to end users faster and in a more useful form, but they can also filter and intelligently compress data to reduce or eliminate the downlink bottleneck. The information extraction step is one of the first steps to a more autonomous satellite.

The need for on-board autonomy in satellite missions is therefore driven by two factors, the delivery of more timely insights to end users and the increasing number of satellites and subsequent quantity of data to be downlinked. The information extraction step is one of the first steps to a more autonomous satellite.

These information extraction abilities are driving research into novel compression methods for different EO applications. These can include text-based alert generation, generating thumbnails of regions-of-interest or completely discarding useless data. In some applications, there is only a small spatial region-of-interest (RoI) in any capture. If the RoI is only

a small part of the data acquired by an instrument when imaging a target, compression gains can be made by applying lossy compression to the area around the target and lossless compression of the RoI. With advances in machine learning (ML), especially deep learning, these RoI can now be identified on-the-fly as data is acquired on-board. The enabling technology for this is hardware acceleration that allows for the deployment of such deep-learning models as part of on-board payload processing chains.

This work on region-of-interest compression builds on previous work at Craft Prospect in developing machine learning powered on-board processing algorithms. These algorithms extract useful information from payload data, but to do so must run efficiently on embedded devices due to the power constraints of satellite missions.

REGION OF INTEREST IDENTIFICATION WITH MACHINE LEARNING

The example application discussed here is a wildfire detection model although the concept could be applied to many segmentation or object detection tasks, any task where an image can be separated into a background and foreground (RoI). For the spacecraft to initially define the RoI of an image, semantic image segmentation is currently being used to identify wildfires in satellite imagery. This method uses a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) to assess images on a per-pixel basis, labelling each pixel with a corresponding binary classification: either “is wildfire” OR “is not wildfire” (i.e., RoI/BG). The output of this takes the form of a binary mask, where feature (RoI) pixels are labelled with a 1, and background (BG) pixels with a 0. The fire masking model used is a custom trained U-Net architecture trained on Landsat and Sentinel-1 data, with the bands available being downselected to three bands where wildfire is visible. The model input is 48x48x3 pixel image chips, and the model outputs a pixel-wise binary mask indicating predicted fire/no-fire. In this application it is imagined that the fire pixels (and possibly a small area around the fire) should be losslessly compressed for ingestion into a ground based computational pipeline for further analysis. For this reason, numerically lossless compression is desirable. Lossy compression can be applied to the background of the image, so long as the context of the RoI is preserved (e.g., larger scale terrain features like ridges, treelines etc. are preserved). A number of selective compression algorithms were tested on wildfire samples after first being assessed on a sample of test images provided by CCSDS.

SELECTIVE COMPRESSION

Selective compression (or RoI encoding) is a useful technique for on-board satellite data compression, used to minimize the storage space of captured imagery while perfectly preserving the data contained within key regions of the image which are identified as important, e.g., wildfire or wildlife data. This allows for more images to be stored at once on the satellite’s limited hardware, as well as reducing the downlink capacity required to transfer the image data to ground.

Numerically lossless (as opposed to near lossless) compression in the region-of-interest preserves values important in metrology and important for further scientific analysis. The properties preserved include independent errors, data unbiased by lossy compression algorithms, correlations in data, and preservation of the potentially well-defined noise model of the sensor that acquired the data. This contrasts with lossy image compression techniques which were developed to preserve the properties of images important to human perception rather than statistical analysis.

The image and mask shown in Fig.1 are passed onto a selective compression algorithm which compresses the RoI losslessly, retaining all information to allow for perfect reconstruction when decoding again - and compress the BG lossily, removing redundant data to allow for higher compression gains. Selective compression algorithms also allow for the configuration of lossy quality, where the trade-off between image quality and storage saved can be altered to suit the current use-case. Selective compression is an active area of research in the space industry, as well as in Medical Imaging where due to the large amounts of data generated, challenges in storage capacity and data transfer are faced. As such, various solutions to the problem have been proposed and tested.

A software prototype has been successfully implemented which is able to perform three different on-board selective compression algorithms on captured image data, with respect to a binary mask provided by the CNN. The level of lossy quality can be specified based on end-user requirements, and the arbitrary expansion of the ROI area around the target feature is supported. All the compression algorithms are feature agnostic: any type of image can be selectively compressed if a corresponding mask is given. Each of the three compression techniques have been evaluated in terms of compression ratio and time taken to compress.

Figure 1 - Fire masking image

GRID PARTITION METHOD

An initial naïve approach that was investigated was to simply segment the image into two separate images containing the RoI and BG sections respectively and compress them accordingly using in-built Unix compression software. This was achieved by segmenting the input image into 8x8 “blocks” and classifying each block as either an RoI block or BG block according to whether it contains an RoI coefficient or not, and then stacking these blocks into two separate image file formats – a TIFF file compressed with the BZip2 package for the lossless file and a lossily compressed JPEG image for the lossy file, which were then concatenated into a single bitstream. Additional information on how to reconstruct the blocks into their original positions in the image was appended to the bitstream as a header to allow for decoding – this was in the form of a list of binary-encoded non-negative integers, where each integer value represents the number of consecutive blocks of the same type (RoI or BG) when scanning the image from left to right then top to bottom, with an additional reference bit used to define the type of the first block of the image. JPEG was chosen as the lossy image file format over the more modern WebP format as notable colour diffusion around the borders of each lossy block was observed after reconstruction: this is because JPEG and WebP compression rely on information from distant neighbouring coefficients to predict the values of each coefficient, resulting in an impractical fuzzy interference effect due to rearranging the image into stacks of non-correlating blocks prior to compression. An example of this method is shown in Fig.2. Preliminary evaluations demonstrated that this method achieved notably better compression results compared to full lossless compression, however the neighbouring block interference effect was still observable for both JPEG and WebP compression (albeit less severe for JPEG) even when setting the lossy quality parameters to be near-lossless, making this approach unlikely to be feasible in a practical context.

DISCRETE WAVELET TRANSFORMS

More sophisticated selective compression algorithms were investigated, all of which built upon the mathematical technique of 2D discrete wavelet transforming (DWT) an image prior to compression. When a wavelet transformation is applied to a signal, a “wavelet” is chosen to model the signal, which is then scaled (expanded or contracted) to create a set of “daughter wavelet” with higher or lower frequencies. Each of these wavelets is then “compared” to the image signal

Figure 2 – An image selectively compressed with the grid partition algorithm. The delta highlights the difference in pixel values between the original and recovered versions of the wildfire image.

at various time-steps across the signal, producing a set of coefficients. When a wavelet represents a portion of the signal well, it results in a larger magnitude coefficient. If it does not represent the signal, the coefficient will equal or be close to zero. In a DWT, the scaling and time-steps used are at predetermined, quantised values, and thus a signal can be reproduced via an inverse DWT operation using the coefficients as an input. For a 2D signal such as an image, the operation is performed twice: after the initial DWT, the coefficients are divided into low (**L**) and high (**H**) frequency sub-bands and the DWT is subsequently performed on these to produce a total of four frequency sub-bands, labelled **LL**, **HL**, **LH** and **HH**.

The **LL** sub-band typically resembles a scaled-down version of the initial image, while the other sub-bands resemble a sparse outline of features within the image. Further DWT operations can be performed on the LL sub-band, where LL can be transformed into its own set of four quadrants **LL₂**, **HL₂**, **LH₂**, **HH₂**. This can be recursively performed on the produced **LL** sub-band **n** times, which produces an **n**-level DWT as seen in Fig.3. Many compression algorithms take advantage of representing an image in this format for several reasons: it can be performed incredibly quickly meaning that there is no significant impact to the time required to encode an image, and the property of many coefficients being near or equal to zero allows for less information to be stored to be able to reconstruct the DWT matrix. An **n**-level DWT also allows for a progressively higher resolution of the image to be produced as the DWT coefficients are decoded, which is useful in contexts where a data stream may be unexpectedly cut off or delayed, or when the downlink capacity of data is limited.

DWTs typically rely on float coefficients, but as computers represent floating point values with finite precision, this will inevitably result in an irreversible decomposition of the original image – thus an integer-to-integer lifting scheme transformation is used instead in the prototype software [1]. A lifting scheme is an alternative method of computing a DWT by predicating and updating even and odd indices of the input signal, which allows for perfect reconstruction and is thus able to achieve numerical lossless compression within the RoI of an image. The 5/3 Daubechies lifting scheme was chosen as a suitable wavelet for the following DWT-based compression algorithms.

SET PARTITIONING IN HIERARCHICAL TREES (SPIHT)

Set Partitioning In Hierarchical Trees (SPIHT) is an image compression algorithm that was first proposed in 1996 [2]. It is an extension of another method called Embedded Zerotrees of Wavelets (EZW). The algorithm evaluates the **n**-level DWT coefficients, and then organises the coefficients in order of “significance”, such that these are encoded (and thus transferred) first. In essence, the coefficients with the largest magnitudes are the most significant as they contribute the most to reconstructing the image. Bit packets can be transferred in such a way that the decoder can reconstruct an increasingly better resolved version of the image as more data is received – therefore lossy compression is achieved by truncating the bitstream at any desired arbitrary point. The parameter used to define the level of lossiness is defined as *BitPlaneStop*, a non-negative integer signifying how many least-significant bits of each coefficient value to truncate from the encoded bitstream.

SPIHT does not natively support RoI compression, but this can be implemented with a pre-and-post processing method known as MaxShift, which is also used in JPEG2000 RoI compression [3]. Prior to encoding, the RoI binary mask is modified such that any coefficient that represents an area within the RoI of the original image is now itself covered by the mask.

Figure 3 – A 2-level DWT of a castle image

The magnitude of all RoI coefficients is then left bit-shifted by N , where N is the minimum value required to scale the magnitude of every RoI coefficient such that they will be considered more significant by the SPIHT algorithm than any BG coefficient. The encoder will then losslessly encode the RoI in its entirety before encoding the background of the image, with the quality defined by the *BitPlaneStop*. The value of N is prepended to the encoded image data, where the decoder will right bit-shift all coefficients with a bit depth of $N+1$ or greater to regain the original DWT matrix. The main drawback of this implementation is that this effectively doubles the bit depth of the DWT image given to the SPIHT algorithm: this potentially results in a significantly longer time to compress the image, as well as possibly running into technical issues when compressing images with a large initial bit depth on hardware with a limited word size.

The implemented SPIHT algorithm was enhanced by additionally entropy coding sets of significance values in the bitstream for each coefficient value, the method for which being defined in the CCSDS-122.0-B-2 recommended standard. This further increases the achieved compression ratios by exploiting the similarities of significance values between adjacent coefficients, at the cost of a slightly longer time required to encode.

JPEG2000

The JPEG2000 compression algorithm works by segmenting the input image into tiles which are then separately Discrete Wavelet Transformed. The JPEG2000 standard natively supports RoI encoding tiles designated as lossless are transformed using a reversible lifting scheme, while lossy tiles are transformed with an irreversible DWT and then further quantized. The same MaxShift method used in the SPIHT implementation is similarly employed to ensure that the RoI will always be fully preserved, and the bitstream can then be truncated at any chosen point to determine the BG lossy quality. JPEG2000 has much more functionality than SPIHT - in terms of compression quality and gains, SPIHT and JPEG have been shown to perform comparatively, although SPIHT has the advantage of being less complex than JPEG2000.

Several software implementations of JPEG2000 were evaluated: OpenJPEG, an open-source version of the standard, was found to be unable to support RoI encoding. The proprietary software package Kakadu was able to provide JPEG2000 selective compression with respect to a given binary mask, however it was unable to run on the spacecraft CPU architecture and thus also unsuitable for use. As a result of these findings, no suitable JPEG2000 implementation was identified. A JPEG2000 implementation which supports both RoI and can be run on ARM architecture was noted as a useful future development in the Further Work section.

CCSDS-122.0-B-2

In 2017, the Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems released the CCSDS 122.0-B-2 recommended standard (hereafter referred to as CCSDS) for image compression [4]. As the CCSDS standard has been specifically developed with implementation on spacecraft in mind, and thus a trade-off has been made between compression performance and complexity of the algorithm, skewing towards lower complexity, meaning it will have a relatively low-power demand. It has a limited set of options, and so is relatively accessible and can be used with limited knowledge of the algorithm.

CCSDS performs a 3-level DWT on the input image before splitting the image into 8x8 blocks, consisting of a coefficient within the lowest-level sub-band of the transformation (LL_3) which is referred to as the DC coefficient of the block, and 63 descendent coefficients which are referred to as the AC coefficients – an example of this is shown in Fig.4 [5]. Blocks are grouped together into segments which each contain a maximum of S blocks, and each block within each segment is compressed independently from each other – this allows for resilience against signal interference, i.e., a bit flipping caused by cosmic rays, as only the affected segment will be corrupted instead of the entire image. Each segment also contains additional information in their header, such as the bit depth required to represent all the AC coefficients in each block it

Figure 4 – The segmenting of a DWT image into 8x8 blocks as defined in the CCSDS standard

contains. Further techniques such as entropy encoding and rice encoding of data are employed to maximize potential compression gains.

Similar to SPIHT, the image data is transmitted in order of most to least significant bits, and thus the *BitPlaneStop* parameter can again be used to define the lossy quality of the encoded image. CCSDS also allows the user to specify how many levels of the DWT should be considered during encoding with the *StageStop* parameter: this can range from encoding only the four coefficients from the lowest level sub-bands, consisting of **LL₃**, **LH₃**, **HL₃** and **LL₃** (*StageStop* = 0), to the full set of coefficients plus additional refinement bits to allow for exact reconstruction (*StageStop* = 3).

The software prototype implements a limited variant of CCSDS, making use of the underlying compression algorithm, but also using a custom header to allow for RoI information to be prepended to the encoded bitstream. As each block is encoded independently, it is feasible to classify them as either an RoI block or BG block depending on whether their DC coefficient is covered by a 1/8-scaled version of the RoI mask. RoI blocks will always be compressed with lossless parameters, i.e., *StageStop* = 3, *BitPlaneStop* = 0, while BG blocks will be lossily compressed according to the parameters defined by the user, i.e., *StageStop* <= 3, *BitPlaneStop* >= 0. The RoI information is encoded in a similar format to the image reconstruction data used in the grid partition compression method, and additionally rice encoded to ensure that the extra storage required is minimized.

PERFORMANCE COMPARISON

The relative performance of each compression algorithm was evaluated using seven monochrome test images from the CCSDS Data Compression Working Group, and three real-world, 5-channel wildfire images captured by satellite data, the properties of which defined in Table 1. Multi-channel images are handled by the prototype software by encoding each channel sequentially and transmitting the data such that the RoI of all channels will be encoded and decoded before the BG data is considered. To ensure that the chosen parameter values for each algorithm resulted in a fair comparison, each test image was given a mean-squared error (MSE) threshold as a measure of the minimum acceptable level of quality for the decoded image, based on their size and bit depth. Each algorithm's parameters were then tuned to achieve the largest possible compression ratio of each image which adheres to the defined MSE threshold.

The three algorithms were run and timed on the Zynq-7000 system-on-chip device used within the satellite architecture, with a Dual-core ARM Cortex-A9 MPCore and 1GB of DDR3 RAM. The wildfire images were omitted from the cumulative timing evaluation due to taking significantly longer to encode compared to the provided CCSDS test data, however it is expected that a future optimized version of the software prototype with support for hardware acceleration will be able to encode these larger multi-band image sets much more quickly.

Table 1 - Test Images

Image	Multiple RoI?	RoI % of image	Original image size (KB)	Image height (px)	Image width (px)	Pixel bit depth	MSE Threshold
lunar	No	14%	32	512	512	8	5
marstest	Yes	12%	32	512	512	8	5
marseille_GB_10b	No	33%	479	528	1856	10	8
sun_spot	No	48%	128	512	512	12	10
pleiades_portdebouc_b3	No	26%	215	1376	320	12	10
solar	No	2%	512	1024	1024	12	10
sar_16bit	No	5%	128	512	512	16	150
wildfire_1	Yes	2%	23428	2000	1600	12	40
wildfire_2	Yes	3%	23428	2000	1600	12	40
wildfire_3	No	13%	23428	2000	1600	12	40

Figure 5a – Compression Ratios for Each Algorithm and Test Image

Figure 5b – Cumulative Time Elapsed for Each Algorithm and Test Image

FUTURE WORK AND CONCLUSIONS

This work has shown that machine learning driven selective compression brings benefits to on-board processing of payload data. The ability to identify regions of interest on-the-fly and then apply compression, which preserves both the numerical values of the region-of-interest and the wider context of the image, unlocks new operational concepts. Various ML models can be run on-board, all identifying RoIs for the compression algorithm to exploit. This achieves higher compression ratios, has been shown to fit within an algorithmic footprint able to run sufficiently well as software on state-of-the-art embedded CPUs available for on-board data processing, and will benefit both on-board storage and data downlink with smaller file sizes generated.

As seen in Fig.5a and Fig.5b, CCSDS achieves the best compression ratios by a significant margin compared to the other evaluated algorithms at the cost of taking the longest time to encode, although this is potentially caused by the

implementation of the algorithm rather than CCSDS itself being slow compared to SPIHT. The naïve grid partition method sees a noticeable improvement in compression ratio compared to a fully lossless BZip compression and performs quickly as the underlying Unix software used for compression will be highly optimized, however this is at the cost of noticeable artifacts and distortion in the image. DWT-based algorithms instead produce a blurry scaled-up lower resolution version of the BG regions of the image, which looks preferable to the human eye even if it produces a similar MSE value. A more sophisticated method for measuring lossiness in image which takes this into account, such as Mean Structural Similarity (MSSIM) would potentially be a better method of comparing the different compression algorithms. The algorithms could also be tested on more real-world applications than fire masking, to see how lossy compression parameter selection can be balanced between compression ratio and the effects on the perception of background image.

The Python prototypes, while successfully able to run on satellite hardware, could see much shorter computation time (and therefore computation per Watt) if rewritten in C or with portions hardware-accelerated with FPGA (especially for CCSDS where each segment can potentially be computed simultaneously). The DWT aspect of the process could be targeted as the simplest block of the process to hardware accelerate. Another software development task could be the development of a suitable JPEG2000 implementation that can be tested on on-board ARM-based hardware.

Future work shall integrate optimized implementations of the demonstrated selective compression functionality within Craft Prospect's component-based software toolbox, the Astral Intelligence Toolbox (AITB) [6]. This comprises configurable hardware and software autonomy-enabling components which can be deployed within CubeSats and other space systems to deliver real-time, on-board data processing and decision making. The AITB is a framework intended to provide rapidly configurable on-board processing and data management solutions while retaining flexibility in integration with hardware and software platforms. Components are designed to be standalone and easily configurable within the framework to create bespoke processing chains such as region-of-interest compression for targets identifiable through ML inference.

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